

[Dr Norman Goldwasser](#) is a Miami Beach based clinical psychologist who has received a doctoral degree in clinical psychology from the University of Virginia's Department of Law and Psychiatry. Additionally, he holds Master's Degrees in the same field from the same university and Bachelor's Degree in clinical psychology from the Johns Hopkins University.

Dr Goldwasser is experienced in treating the effects of trauma, such as obsessive compulsive disorders, adult and adolescent ADHD, sex addiction and substance abuse, sexual issues, personality disorders, especially narcissism, and depression. He has a 30 years experience in using the EMDR (Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing) treatment, an innovative methodology designed to relieve continuing psychological distress from trauma.

Moreover, he gives speeches at national and international events as an experienced professional.

Furthermore, [this expert psychologist](#) provides his coaching services to businesses and organizations. Additionally, he has provides also educational services to schools.

Over the course of [his career](#), he has received a number of awards and recognitions about his work.

In 2015, Dr Goldwasser has been named Top Psychologist in Miami Beach by the International Association of Health Care Professionals. Some of the awards he has received include Guest of Honor Award at the Chai Lifeline Dinner, the Educational Leadership Award from Yeshiva Elementary, Guest of Honor for Congregation Ohr Chaim, Honor Society of the National Conference of Synagogue Youth, and Founders Award at the Collegiate Learning Exchange of the University of Miami.